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ISC 2025

XX INTERNATIONAL SILAGE CONFERENCE

JULY 21-24, 2025 | GAINESVILLE, FL USA

CONFERENCE PROGRAM BOOK

HOST ORGANIZATIONS

GLOBAL FOOD
SYSTEMS INSTITUTE

ANIMAL
SCIENCES

UF | IFAS
UNIVERSITY of FLORIDA

UF/IFAS AGRONOMY
DEPARTMENT

FORAGE TEAM

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Name Badge

Your name badge is your entry pass to all networking events at ISC 2025, so please wear it throughout the conference. As a reminder, due to spacing constraints, *guests are not permitted*.

AGENDA-AT-A-GLANCE

Sunday, July 20, 2025	
3:30pm–6:30pm	Registration Opens Exhibitor Move-In Poster Installation
4:30pm–5:30pm	Planning Committee Meeting
5:30pm–6:30pm	Welcome Social
Monday, July 21, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
7:30am–8:30am	Poster Installation
8:30am–11:30am	Plenary Session
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch & Presentation
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
2:00pm–5:00pm	Plenary Session
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
6:00pm–7:30pm	Dinner Banquet
Tuesday, July 22, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
2:00pm–5:00pm	Concurrent Sessions
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
Wednesday, July 23, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–12:30pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
12:30pm–2:00pm	Group Lunch, Presentation, & Awards
2:00pm–3:15pm	Plenary Session
3:15pm–4:15pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
4:15pm–5:00pm	Closing Plenary Session
5:00pm	Conference Concludes
Thursday, July 24, 2025	
7:30am–5:30pm	Optional Off-property Field Tour

POSTER DIRECTORY

(Posters are listed in order by topic, poster session, then by presenter last name.)

POSTER VIEWING 1

POSTER VIEWING 2

POSTER VIEWING 3

Advancing Silage Production for Small Holders						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
1	Muhammad	Shaheryar	Bahauddin Zakariya University	Pakistan	Ensuring Quality Feed Through Silage-Making for Smallholders	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
2	Olabode	Olanrewaju	Calvary Ministries CAPRO	Nigeria	Silage, A Potential Solution to the Farmer-Herder Conflicts that Have Killed Tens of Thousands in West Africa- A Missionary's Perspective	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
3	Nouhoun	Zampaligre	Centre National de Recherche Scientifique et Technologique (CNRST)	Burkina Faso	Small Scale Corn Silage for Quality Fodder Conservation in the Integrated Crop-Livestock Systems of the Sahel	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Aerobic Stability						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
5	Angelika	Borkowska	Volac International Ltd	United Kingdom	Amino Acids in Lucerne Silage: 2. Effects of Inoculation	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
7	Kristin	Rang	University of Bonn	Germany	Impact of Ensiling and Storage Temperature on the Aerobic Stability of Maize Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
10	Hana	Synkova	NutriVet s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Monitoring Changes in Temperature of Fermented Feeds and Their Aerobic Stability	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
4	Mukti	Bhandari	University of Delaware	United States	Effect of Inoculant on Alfalfa Silage Challenged with Air Stress and Loosely Packed Conditions	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
8	Thiago	da Silva	Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia	Brazil	Aerobic Deterioration of Diets Containing Cassava Shoot and Root Silages	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
6	Shane	Cronin	IFF Nutrition and Biosciences	United States	Effect of Laboratory Bag Silo Plastic Type on Fermentation of Corn Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
9	Joao	Daniel	State University of Maringa	Brazil	Obligate Heterofermentative Lactic Acid Bacteria Decrease Losses During Storage and Feedout in Corn Silage Fermented for Long Period	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Baleage and Other Silages						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
16	Joos	Latré	University of Applied Sciences and Arts	Belgium	Ensiling Moist Cereal-Legume Intercrops: A Promising Conservation Technique, Reducing Anti-Nutritional Factors in Faba Beans	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
11	Daniel Jose	Cavalli Vieira	University of Wisconsin-Madison	United States	Survey of Fiber Quality of Cover Crops Used as Forage to Dairy Cattle in Wisconsin	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
14	Ivan	Eisner	Novonesis	Denmark	Improving the Quality of Haylage for Horses by Adding a Biological Silage Additive	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
17	Anibal Coutinho	Rego	Federal University of Ceara	Brazil	Dry Matter Concentration Affects the Relationships with Variables Linked to Cassava Haylage Characteristics	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22

Silage Feeding and Utilization (continued)						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
144	Tiago	Del Valle	Federal University of Santa Maria	Brazil	Citrus Essential Oil as Silage or Feed Additive has No Effect on Sheep Feed Intake and Daily Gain	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
147	Ewald	Kramer	ISF GmbH	Germany	Influence of <i>L. Diolivorans</i> Inoculant on the Carbon Footprint of Corn Silage in a Biogas Plant	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
150	Luiz Gustavo	Nussio	University of São Paulo	Brazil	Propionic Acid-Based Additive on Aerobic Stability of Total Mixed Ration : Dairy Cows Performance and Feed Frequency	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
152	Meelis	Ots	Estonian University of Life Sciences	Estonia	Effects of Silage Made From Fungicide-Treated Grass on Dairy Cows' Performance	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
156	Hana	Synkova	NutriVet s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Quality of Silages from Selected Pea and Faba Bean Varieties in The Malá Haná Region, Czech Republic	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
126	Saleh	Umar	Lanzou University	China	Influence of Inoculated Corn-Alfalfa Mixed Silage on Growth Performance of Hu Sheep	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
159	Johanna	Witt	ISF GmbH	Germany	Effect of Different Silage Inoculants on Digestibility Parameters and Metabolizable Energy in Vivo - A Meta-Analysis	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
141	Thiago	da Silva	Federal Rural University of the Amazon	Brazil	Cost Comparison Between Corn and Cassava Peel Silage in Diets for Feedlot Beef Cattle	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
145	Vaclav	Jambor	NutriVet s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Selection and Nutritive Value of Different Hybrids of Maize Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
148	Marjukka	Lamminen	University of Helsinki	Finland	In Vitro Rumen Fermentation of Grass, Clover and Corn Silage-Based Diets with Different Protein Feeds	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
149	Klaus	Hünting	Saxony State Office for the Environment Agriculture and Geology	Germany	Review: Dm Losses of Grass and Other Forages from Harvest Through Conservation, Storage and Feedout to Intake	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
153	Odilon	Pereira	Federal University of Vicosa	Brazil	Intake and Digestibility of Beef Cattle Fed Corn Silage or Total Mixed Ration	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
155	Richard	Scuderi	Lallemand	United States	Effects of Inoculated Corn Silage on Fermentation, Aerobic Stability, and Feed Preference in Holstein Heifers	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
158	Federico	Tarnonsky	University of Florida	United States	Sorghum Silage as a Feed Alternative for Backgrounding Heifers in Florida	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
160	Dongmei	Xu	Lanzhou University	China	Bacteriocin-Producing <i>Lactiplantibacillus Plantarum</i> Inoculated Alfalfa Silage Promoted Digestion and Production Performance of Dairy Goats	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23

Silage Experimental Design and Analysis

#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
162	Kevin	Panke-Buisse	USDA-ARS	United States	Extraction of Metagenomic Quality DNA From Corn and Alfalfa Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
161	Gerd-Christian	Maack	University of Bonn	Germany	Effect of a Silage Inoculant Containing <i>L. Diolivorans</i> on CO2 Emissions of Corn Silage During Anaerobic and Aerobic Storage	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
163	Laura	Pieper	Dr. Pieper, Technologie- und Produktentwicklung GmbH	Germany	Use of Optical pH-Measurement in Early Silage Fermentation Trials	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
164	Saurav	Tuteja	NDDDB Dairy Services	India	Total Mixed Ration (TMR) to Enhance Dairy Productivity in Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23